

and *S. furcifera* were allowed feeding access on diseased rice plants for one day. Each insect was tested for transmission ability by serial daily transfers onto a test plant, Taichung Native 1, in a test tube.

Nilaparvata bakeri nymphs were

allowed feeding access on diseased rice plants for 17 hours (overnight), and were reared on a host, *Leersia hexandra*, for 7 days (incubation period). Transmission ability was tested by alternately putting the insect for 16 hours on a test rice plant and 8 hours on *Leersia hex-*

andra. *N. bakeri* would die if fed only on rice plants.

N. virescens, *R. dorsalis*, and *S. furcifera* did not transmit rice ragged stunt virus but *N. bakeri* did. ■

Resistance of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*, the rice bacterial blight pathogen, to phenazine

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The bacteriostatic effect of phenazine on *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*, the

rice bacterial blight pathogen, under laboratory conditions was confirmed.

Phenazine-resistant variants of the bacterial strains were easily obtained by the paper disc method on peptone sucrose agar plates (Table 1). The number of phenazine-resistant variants was not correlated with virulence. Variants derived from strains of pv. *oryzae* that had lost their virulence seemed to

be more virulent to RD1, a susceptible rice cultivar than the parent strains. Some variants obtained from other virulent strains were similar to and others different from parental strains.

Two days after RD1 was inoculated with both wild type parental strains and variants derived from them, derivative variants produced longer lesions than parental strains (Table 2). Variants derived from different groups appeared to increase in virulence in most strains tested, but only a few were similar to the parental strains.

Since it is relatively easy to obtain the phenazine-resistant variants, the efficiency of the chemical *in vitro* should be monitored before a recommendation is made under field conditions. ■

Electron microscopy of particles of rice tungro virus complex

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Rice plants infected with ragged stunt virus at IRRI were homogenized in Turin. Two types of particles, apparently those of rice tungro virus complex, were found by electron microscopy, in addition to particles of ragged stunt virus, indicating that the diseased plants were multiple infected (IRRN 3[2]:9, 1978).

The viruses were purified from the sap of the infected plants using Freon, Nonidet P40, ultracentrifugation through sucrose cushions, and density gradient centrifugation in cesium sulfate. After negative staining, the preparation was examined under an electron microscope whose magnification was calibrated with a diffraction grating replica.

Table 1. Inhibition effect of phenazine on strains of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* and phenazine-resistant variants from the inhibition zone. Bangkok, Thailand.

Strain	Virulence group	Inhibition zone ^a (cm)	Colony variants ^a (no.)
TB7535	0	6.6	2.6
TB7612	0	5.5	0.2
TB7618	0	4.2	22.7
TB7803	0	6.2	124.7
TB7811	0	6.1	0.7
TB7817	0	8.1	4.8
TB7824	0	8.4	5.1
TB7615	I	5.4	43.7
TB7804	I	4.5	31.3
TB7810	I	5.0	5.1
TB7837	I	8.5	187.9
TB7212	II	7.5	28.8
TB7536	II	6.1	1.9
TB7805	II	4.2	6.3
TB7834	II	7.7	79.6

^aMean of 9 plates.

Table 2. Effect of phenazine application on bacterial blight of RD1 caused by wild type parental strains and phenazine-resistant variants Bangkok, Thailand.

Strain	Lesion ^a (cm)			
	Phenazine treated		Check	
	Wild type	Variant	Wild type	Variant
TB7535	0.9	5.9	1.4	5.8
TB7672	0.3	7.6	1.0	2.1
TB7678	1.8	27.5	3.4	24.4
TB7803	1.5	28.0	3.4	26.0
TB7811	0.6	13.4	5.9	20.9
TB7817	1.1	17.8	5.0	22.6
TB7824	0.2	0.8	3.5	9.0
TB7615	3.0	23.5	12.1	24.2
TB7804	0.9	23.3	8.7	27.5
TB7810	10.3	13.2	11.3	22.5
TB7837	1.1	22.8	26.2	29.3
TB7212	0.2	17.1	17.9	22.5
TB7536	16.5	16.9	27.9	29.9
TB7895	20.4	22.5	24.8	25.7
TB7834	1.2	23.9	27.1	26.8

^aMean of 3 replications.

Isometric and bacilliform particles of rice tungro virus complex.

The presumed tungro complex particles were isometric and bacilliform (see figure). The isometric particles were 27-28 nm in diameter when negatively stained in 2% uranyl acetate (UA) and 30 nm in diameter in 1% neutral sodium phosphotungstate (PTA). The bacilliform particles were 23 nm in diameter in UA and 31-33 nm in diameter in PTA. The length of the bacilliform particles was variable in both stains. Apparently undamaged particles with both ends rounded were 110-190 nm long in UA, although no particular modal length was detected.

Hibino and associates reported in *Phytopathology* 68:1412, 1978, on the negatively stained appearance and dimensions of particles of the tungro complex. They used PTA only on crude preparations. Our results in PTA confirm their measurements of particles in the same stain. However, we note that the bacilliform particles particularly appeared damaged in our PTA preparations. We think that the substantially greater diameter compared to that in UA was due to artifactual swelling or flattening. ■

second. When nonviruliferous females were crossed with nonviruliferous males of both species, none of the progeny became infective.

These results indicate that *N. virescens* is also a vector of RDV, transmitting the virus in a persistent manner with transovarial passage. ■

Survey of rice diseases in the Vietnamese Mekong delta from 1978 to 1980

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Rice diseases in the Vietnamese Mekong delta were surveyed from 1978 to 1980, with 69 cooperators of the PPD, faculty of Agriculture, University of Can Tho. The results showed 25 diseases in rice fields and 6 fungi on stored grain. Blast, sheath blight, bacterial blight, and ufra were the most important diseases (see table).

Blast and sheath blight appeared everywhere in the delta, but were most severe in three regions.

Blast was severe in Tiengiang region and the southern part of Haugiang region (Fig. 1). In Tiengiang, blast was important in January, February, March, and July, with highest peaks in January and July every year. Node blast occurred in March.

In the southern part of Haugiang province, node blast was common in December-January, and leaf blast, in July. An epidemic of leaf blast in July 1978 destroyed more than 300 ha of seedling nurseries in the main season crop.

Severe sheath blight occurrence was observed in two regions — the northwestern region of the delta encompassing the whole of Angiang province and the northern part of Haugiang province, and in Tiengiang regions (Fig. 2).

Bacterial blight and ufra diseases were important in the rainy season and in deepwater areas. They sometimes caused severe losses in some limited areas.

Kernel smut broke out from February to April 1979 as an epidemic in the northwestern part of the delta. More

A new insect vector of rice dwarf virus

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Rice dwarf virus (RDV) is transmitted in a persistent manner with transovarial passage by *Nephotettix cincticeps*, *N. nigropictus*, and *Recilia dorsalis*.

N. virescens and *N. cincticeps* were collected 1974-1977 from rice fields in Fujian. Infectivity was tested on variety Zhin Zhuai 11 at the 3-leaf stage. Of 988 *N. virescens* and 969 *N. cincticeps* tested, 4.3% and 4.9% of the insects, respectively, were capable of causing

RDV infection in rice plants, indicating that infective insects of both species exist under natural conditions.

After an acquisition feeding of 3-4 days and a latent period of about 9 days both species transmitted the RDV (see table). RDV was persistent in the insect vector.

There was transovarial passage of RDV in both species. When viruliferous females were crossed with nonviruliferous males of *N. virescens*, the progeny became infective at 8% for the first generation and 4% for the second. When viruliferous females were crossed with nonviruliferous males of *N. cincticeps*, the progeny became infective at 19% for the first generation and 12% for the

Transmission of rice dwarf virus by two species of *Nephotettix*, Shaxian, China.

Species	Insects tested (no.)	Infective insects (%)	Latent period (days)			
			In insect		In plant	
			Av	Range	Av	Range
<i>N. cincticeps</i>	544	35	9.4	6-32	10.6	7-48
<i>N. virescens</i>	567	31	9.0	7-21	12.4	8-38